

NECESSITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE SCIENCE OF SOCIAL PEDAGOGY

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Abstract: Today, interest in social pedagogy has arisen on the basis of the development of the needs of society and the social order of the state. The article discusses the need for social pedagogy and its significance.

Keywords: social pedagogy, education and upbringing, sociology, market economy, social relations.

НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ И ЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В НАУКЕ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ

Аннотация: Сегодня интерес к социальной педагогике возник на основе развития потребностей общества и социального заказа государства. В статье обсуждается необходимость социальной педагогики и ее значение.

Ключевые слова: социальная педагогика, образование и воспитательная деятельность, социология, рыночная экономика, социальные отношения.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the Republic is undergoing political, economic, educational and educational-cultural reforms. New principles of humanization of social structures, laws of the attitude of the market economy, changes in ideological and moral principles lead to aggravation of social problems such as unemployment, material shortages, lack of control of children, separation of families, absent social workers-alcoholism, drug addiction, crime, prostitution. In this case, first of all, children, and then adults, are in love with social assistance. In such conditions, a demand arises for a social educator as a specialist who solves pedagogical issues that depend on the social problems of society, assisting a person in the process of its socialization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The need for social pedagogy was required by the following circumstances:

First of all, today it is required to identify the reasons for the contradiction between the purpose of education and training and some of its results, and to identify ways to eliminate them. This requirement aroused the need to bring into the world of pedagogy sociology, which deals with relations in society. Because human activity, having a conscious nature, constitutes a specific object of the science of sociology. The understanding of each person's place in society, his own self, the embodiment of life-moral norms, the manifestation of these spiritual and moral qualities in society, the cooperation of the disciplines of pedagogy and sociology in the upbringing of young people in harmony with our social life, our time, plays a special role. Although education is a social phenomenon and a pedagogical process.

Secondly, it requires a new methodology based on the coherence of pedagogical and sociological concepts in order to find solutions to new problems, such as determining the causal nature of the social origin of the spiritual emptiness in the minds of some members of society, creating a mechanism for solving them. When forming a human personality, it is necessary to take into account the natural (hereditary) and social characteristics in it, the possibilities of its higher nervous activity. It is necessary to organize its upbringing on the basis of knowledge of the laws of self-education, adaptation to conditions, orientation to a certain object on the basis of the biological and subjective (personal aspects) of the human body. Opportunities of internal and external influence in the process of personality formation based on such important features as

mutual understanding, features of youth activity of the educational process, awareness of the essence, freedom and pride of the individual, relying on Democratic, humanitarian and national principles, the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in them is a period requirement. The transformation of the consciousness, thinking of people into society in a positive way is associated with socio - educational processes. It is important to study it scientifically. The problems caused by the involvement of pedagogy and sociology also attract the close attention of scientists from Uzbekistan.

Thirdly, social relations in the conditions of a market economy and the role of the state in this, information, teacher-student relations, personnel problems, the reasons for the weakness in the spirituality of young people, their identification, verification, solution, social activity professional skills, as well as moral and ideological reforms taking place in independent Uzbekistan, as a whole, society with the The main thing is that in social life there are such situations in which children will need the help of a social educator, who in such a difficult situation will mentally be an ointment for themselves by teenagers, educators. Hence, the need for a social educator, as well as a social psychologist, is felt in the foundations of our today's society.

RESULTS

Individuals who have lost hope in life, do not believe in themselves, are unable to independently solve life problems, expect human help, understanding, companion attachment to his grief. Instilling self-confidence in such individuals with their word and activity, helping them to realize their capabilities, is the main task of a social educator. This direction of Science, which argues about the processes taking place in their minds, the influence of reality on people in our social life, is emerging today as a social order.

Hence the emergence of social pedagogy manifested itself on the basis of social necessity.

Social pedagogy and pedagogical sociology is a branch of pedagogical science that studies the laws of socialization of children and social education and social education of children. That is, upbringing is not just educational institutions, it has its own appearance in all aspects of the public, society as a whole.

DISCUSSION

Social pedagogy is a science that explains the thoughts, beliefs, ideas, views, feelings, various forms of behavior that are formed in people during the process of collaborative work activities in society. The main task of social pedagogy is to explain the pedagogical nature and laws of each individual's existence in society, the complex interactions that he establishes with individuals similar to him, observing social norms, and the employees formed by their influence.

Social pedagogy has a long and deep tradition both in Uzbekistan and in other countries of the world. Nevertheless, during the former Soviet regime, the achievements of social pedagogy were ignored. That is why Social Pedagogy as a new area includes not only the Departments of state and public bodies of socio-pedagogical specialists, but also a system that trains specialists, as well as a research base of socio-pedagogical activity.

CONCLUSIONS

After the formation of work on the accumulation of social pedagogical experience in practice in social pedagogical and youth living complexes, associations consisting of employees of different ages, the whip of schools with social institutions changed. On this basis, the process of Pedagogy of social interaction developed intensively. So, unlike the disciplines and educational institutions that are engaged in educational education, social pedagogy is associated with all the facets of our social life.

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